

MODERN PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

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ANNOTATION

This article discusses the problems of improving the quality of education today, their ideas and considerations for overcoming and defining prospects, including the improvement of curricula, the organization of scientific research in accordance with the requirements of the time, the use of foreign experience in this area, the professional qualities of the learners and the development of logical thinking operations.

KEY WORDS:

Psychology, human activity, pedagogy, biology, physiology, antiquity, electronic computing, educational standards, paradigm, information and communication.

Emphasis is placed on the psychological and psychopedagogical aspects of the use of information technology. Research such as the impact of distance education on students 'cognitive and personal development is of great importance today. In today's world, the labor market places high demands on highly educated professionals and their competitiveness. The training of such professionals should focus on new standards of competency-based higher education and involve the formation of a number of general cultural and professional competencies of students. In addition to cognitive abilities, it enhances the importance of qualities such as responsibility, self-confidence, self-discipline, communication skills, and their role in successful learning.

Modern Psychology is a science consisting of a multidisciplinary system of psychological knowledge, with its own research subject, consisting of many disciplines. Advances in psychology play a key role in realizing and mobilizing individual potential, while at the same time increasing productivity. Modern psychology uses computer technology, in-depth study of the psyche with the help of electrical and chemical means. Today, with the rapid development of science and technology, the volume of many scientific knowledge, concepts and imaginations is growing rapidly. On the one hand, this ensures its differentiation due to the development of new areas of science and technology, and on the other hand, there is a process of integration between the sciences. In this context, the demand for qualified teachers is growing, and it is necessary to

cultivate creative teachers who have a thorough knowledge of the fundamentals of science, methods of pedagogy and psychology, high professional training and the ability to apply modern innovative pedagogical and information technologies.

Interactive methods based on pedagogical technologies, in which the learner:

- focuses on independent and creative work
- creative research in small groups;
- expanding the scope of knowledge, scientific outlook
- free thinking;
- activity, communication, cooperation, experience of various life events
- discussion;
- aimed at developing the ability to work independently, creative thinking and team management, decision-making and organization of its implementation
- There are such views as attention.

Indeed, in the implementation of the updated education system, it is important that every educator has the ability to regularly study educational innovations and apply them consistently in their work. Improving the quality of education, the relevance of teachers' knowledge and professional skills to the requirements of the time, the rational use of innovative educational technologies in teaching, the effectiveness of organized lessons, the use of pedagogical and information technologies in each subject required to ensure the transition.

Today, in order to modernize the education system, introduce innovative teaching technologies, train young people with such professional qualities as independence, creativity, initiative, entrepreneurship and encourage teachers, great work is being done in our country. However, the results of the analysis and study show that there are still problems in our education system. Including:

- Lack of qualified teachers in educational institutions, incomplete consideration of reforms in the development of curricula and programs implemented in their training, and their outdated content;
 - Lack of training by teachers aimed at developing the intellectual abilities of students;
- Incomplete cooperation between educational institutions;
- Lack of systematic and innovative activities to strengthen the theoretical and practical knowledge of students and the implementation of creative ideas of talented youth;
- Problems affecting the education system, such as the inability of students to argue and express themselves in the classroom. Overcoming these problems requires the continuous training of educators, the use of alternative methods,

and the implementation of tasks such as continuous research. Since ancient times, psychological knowledge has developed on the basis of philosophy and medical sciences. Experiments of the XIX century in general play a special role in the development of psychology. During this period, a set of methods began to be used to study the psychological reality. The world is currently undergoing an important transition from an industrial society to a post-industrial society, which marks an important historical transition and is known as the age of information technology. Information and communication technologies are being actively introduced in all spheres of human activity. They, of course, affect a wide range of social activities, such as education. The paradigm of education in the information society is changing. These changes are due to the fact that the majority of the population in developed countries have access to open data. These changes place great emphasis on personal characteristics that influence the achievement of a particular social status. Active in new telecommunications and information technologies As a result of our development, we have achieved a qualitatively new state of information processing in the education system. This means that it is very important today to summarize and apply in practice the work we are doing on the quality of our systematized education, using advanced foreign experience. To this end, the widespread introduction of modern pedagogical technologies, educational programs and teaching materials based on international educational standards will be an important task in the future.

In short, through the implementation of these tasks, it is necessary to effectively use foreign experience in the training of qualified specialists, based on which to develop new approaches in educational institutions to the organization of training. Because the educational process is the main area of pedagogical creativity, it is necessary to organize and manage it, an innovative approach to the development of students through knowledge, independence, creativity, collaboration, deepening of professional competencies. draws attention to the quality of the lim. Overcoming the existing shortcomings and problems in improving the quality of education, clearly defining the goals and objectives in this direction, the use of world-renowned experience, the use of information technology in combination with pedagogical technologies to improve the quality of professional training of future professionals serves to improve, which increases the efficiency of the process. Clarification of educational goals, the use of various technological methods used in the process of teaching and learning, focus on content, leads to the development and improvement of educational institutions.

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